

Liposomal Anisotropy — a Signal for Lipid-Drug Interaction at the Interface

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Using liposomal membranes of different lipids like egg lecithin, sphingomyelin and dipalmitoyl phosphatidylcholine, we have studied the effect of the hydrophilic drugs chloroquine sulphate, nicotinic acid etc. on the membrane anisotropy, which is an index of the membrane microviscosity. The observed effect is presumably through the charge-charge interaction between the lipid head group and the hydrophilic drugs at the lipid water interface.

Transport across biological membrane is probably the single most important biological process necessary for the survival of the living system and membrane fluidity is one of the few major physical parameters which controls this transport process. A dramatic alteration in membrane fluidity occurs due to the phase transition from gel to liquid crystalline state exhibited by the lipid bilayer systems¹. The triggering of phase transition and hence the fluidity profile of the lipid bilayers, can be monitored by varieties of external agents; drugs being one of them.

Drugs, whose action on living system is a membrane based phenomenon, can affect the membrane fluidity in more than one way. The lipophilic drugs influence it by their direct incorporation in the membrane lipid matrix. When administered *in vivo*, drugs like chlorpromazine can accumulate inside the membrane and affect membrane permeability through alteration of the fatty acid composition². In comparison to these membrane penetrating drugs, the activity of hydrophilic drugs is controlled by the nonspecific charge-charge and hydrophobic interaction at the membrane-water interface only³.

Using liposomal membrane of different lipids as a working model for biological membrane, this presentation gives an account of our study on the effect of different hydrophilic drugs on the anisotropy/microviscosity of the membrane lipid domains through their interaction with the polar head group of the lipid molecules at the interface. The anisotropy has been measured in terms of the fluorescence polarization of the 1,6-diphenyl-1,3,5-hexatriene (DPH), used as the reporter molecule. The ratio of drug bound lipid molecules to free lipids has been estimated in case of the drug chloroquine sulphate (CQS), which is a water-soluble antimalarial drug having blood schizontocidal activity against several susceptible strains of plasmodium. Our result shows that the drug stabilises the liposomal membrane⁴. Using liposomal membrane of a mixture of phospholipid, sphingomyelin and cholesterol (when mixed in required proportion, this system mimics the rat liver plasma membrane in its lipid composition), we have studied how the anticholesterol and vasodilatory drug nicotinic acid, which

is a compound of toxic alkaloid nicotine, can inhibit the intermediate fluid condition induced by cholesterol in the liposomal system⁵.

Results and Discussion

In Fig. 1, $\ln n$ is plotted against $1/T$ for a DPH-probed mixed liposomal system (Sph : DPPC in molar ratio 1 : 4). The figure indicates a distinct phase transition around 30–40°, intermediate between that of DPPC and Sph⁶. Cholesterol was incorporated into the mixed lipid system in the molar ratio 3 : 1 for DPPC and cholesterol (this is approximately equal to the molar ratio of cholesterol and phospholipid in rat liver plasma membrane⁷ and Fig. 1b shows

Fig. 1. Microviscosity as a function of temperature in DPH-probed mixed lipid liposomes : (a) DPPC : Sph in 4 : 1 molar ratio, DPPC concentration = 10^{-4} M; (b) cholesterol added to (a) (DPPC : cholesterol in 3 : 1 molar ratio); (c) NA added to (b) (cholesterol : NA in 1 : 1 molar ratio); (d) NA added to (a) (lipid : NA in 1 : 1 molar ratio) (Ref 5)

that the fluidity has increased below and decreased above the phase transition temperature. This is in agreement with the effect of cholesterol of producing an intermediate fluid condition in the biological membrane⁸. When NA is added to the cholesterol-incorporated liposome, for a 1 : 1 molar ratio of both, it modifies the fluidity profile by eliminating the effect of cholesterol to some extent (Fig. 1c). In the absence of cholesterol, also, NA creates a more fluid environment for the probe molecules (Fig. 1d).

From these observations we may conclude that NA affects the fluidity of liposomal membrane probably by interacting with the head group of the lipid molecules, which then secondarily affects the motion of the fatty acyl chains. The administration of NA produces a detectable vasodilatory effect *in vivo*⁹. However, the exact nature of interaction *in vivo* is totally different from that observed *in vitro*, as the drug metabolism plays an important role there.

In Fig. 2, the temperature profile of the fluorescence anisotropy of DPH probed DPPC liposome and its change due to CQS incorporation has been plotted. It seems that the drug does not change the phase transition temperature T_c (the temperature corresponding to the point of inflexion).

Fig. 2. Fluorescence anisotropy as a function of temperature in DPH-probed DPPC liposome (lipid concentration = 10^{-4} M). Molar ratio of lipid to drug : (a) 1 : 0, (b) 1 : 0.04, (c) 1 : 0.08, (d) 1 : 0.12 (Ref. 4).

Below T_c , the drug rigidifies the membrane and the effect increases with increase in drug concentration. The electrostatic interaction between the drug and the head group of the lipid molecules leads to the adsorption of CQS molecules on the liposomal surface and secondarily hinders the motion of the fatty acyl chains of DPPC. When the phase transition starts, the drug molecules probably are gradu-

ally released from the liposomal surface, the membrane gets fluidized and the anisotropy value decreases.

In Fig. 3 we have plotted x , the fraction of lipid molecules motionally restricted by their interaction with the drug molecules, with respect to the molar ratio of drug to lipid. The curve shows that as the drug concentration increases, x increases and tends to a saturation value. This

Fig. 3. Variation of the fraction of motionally restricted lipids (x) with respect to the molar ratio of lipid to drug (Ref. 4).

indicates that all the drug molecules are participating and they get absorbed to the surface of the liposome as long as there is accessible space. Thus it can be stated that the hydrophilic drug CQS modifies the membrane orderliness by its interaction with the head group of the lipid molecules at the membrane-water interface.

Experimental

Spectral grade solvents (E. Merck) were used. Dipalmitoylphosphatidylcholine (DPPC), 1,6-diphenyl-1,3,5-hexatriene (DPH) and sphingomyelin (Sph) (all Sigma) and nicotinic acid (NA) (Loba) were used as such. CQS was a gift of Central Drug Laboratory, Calcutta. Liposomes were prepared by sonication of an aqueous dispersion of measured amounts of lipids¹⁰. Cholesterol and NA were incorporated into the liposomes following the procedure described earlier¹¹. For preparing liposomes of mixed lipids, Sph and DPPC in a molar ratio of 1 : 4 was used⁵.

For fluorescence measurement, 25 μ l of DPH solution (4×10^{-4} M in *N,N*-dimethylformamide) was added to the sonicated aqueous dispersion of liposome (with/without the drug) and DPH : lipid molar ratio was maintained at 1 : 200. A Perkin-Elmer MPF 44B fluorescence spectrometer was used to measure the steady state fluorescence anisotropy (r)¹².

$$r = (I_1 - I_2) / (I_1 + 2I_2)$$

where, I_1 and I_2 are the vertical and horizontal components of 428 nm emission band of DPH in liposomes, while

the sample is being excited by the vertical component of light from an excitation monochromator at 360 nm. An estimation for the microviscosity ($n + 15\%$)⁶ of the probe environment can be made as follows :

$$n = (I_1 / I_2 - 1) / (0.73 - 0.27(I_1 / I_2))$$

The fluorescence intensities were calculated after properly eliminating the light scattering effect and all measurements were made in a thermostated cell maintained at constant temperatures.

The number of motionally restricted lipid molecules can be estimated from the fact that the hydrophilic drug molecules adhere to the surface of the liposomal membrane due to their electrostatic interaction with the polar head group of the lipids. As a result, this interaction secondarily restricts the motion of the hydrocarbon chain of the lipid molecules. Following the method of Hubre *et al.*¹³, we estimated the fraction of motionally restricted lipids,

$$X = L_B / L$$

where, L_B and L are the number of lipid molecules bound to drug molecules and total number of lipid molecules respectively. In terms of r , r_b and r_f , referring to the fluorescence anisotropy characterising respectively, the average value, due to motionally restricted lipid associated with drug molecules (L_B) and due to the remaining bulk of the lipid molecules not associated with drug molecules, x can be calculated as

$$r' - r = x(r'_b - r_b) + (1 - x)(r'_f - r_f)$$

where prime refers to values at a lower temperature.

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